

1 **A neurochemical basis to ADHD.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We used patient-derived lymphoblastoid cell lines derived and microarray sequencing of total gene
8 expression to study the molecular basis of attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD). We describe here
9 activation of the adrenoreceptor beta 1 ADRB1 in the cells of humans with ADHD. CCL17 expression was
10 defective in ADHD patient cells while CXCL13 was enriched for. Interferon gamma was over-expressed in
11 ADHD patient cells. The KCNMB1 channel was repressed, and the OXTR receptor was induced. We
12 presented here key aspects of an ADHD gene expression signature in humans which contained a
13 surprising immunologic component.

14 Citations

- 15 1. Demontis, D., Duan, J., Hsu, Y.H.H., Pintacuda, G., Grove, J., Nielsen, T.T., Thirstrup, J.,
16 Martorana, M., Botts, T., Satterstrom, F.K. and Bybjerg-Grauholm, J., 2026. Rare genetic variants confer a
17 high risk of ADHD and implicate neuronal biology. Nature, 649(8098), pp.909-917.
- 18 2. Okie, S., 2006. ADHD in adults. New England Journal of Medicine, 354(25), p.2637.

19 GSE52889